

Surface tension studies for iso-octylphenoxypolyethoxy ethanol (TX-100) in water and in aqueous sodium chloride at various temperatures

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Surface tension have been measured for iso-octyl phenoxy polyethoxy ethanol (TX-100) in water and in aqueous NaCl at 288.15, 293.15 and 298.15 K. The values of critical micelle concentration (CMC), maximum surface excess concentration ($\Gamma_{\max}$) and minimum area per molecule ($A_{\min}$) of the surfactant at air-liquid interface have been evaluated. Thermodynamic parameters of micellization and those of adsorption have also been evaluated. The micellization processes appear to be endothermic in nature while negative values of ΔG_m^0 and positive values of ΔS_m^0 support its spontaneity.

A number of reports have appeared on the surface and thermodynamic properties for surfactant in aqueous electrolyte

solutions at temperatures 298 K or above, yet, the data for such systems at low temperatures is scanty¹⁻³. In the pres-

Fig. 1. Plot of surface tension (γ) as a function of $\log [TX-100]$: (a) TX-100 + H₂O. (b) TX-100 + H₂O + NaCl (0.025 M). (c) TX-100 + H₂O + NaCl (0.050 M). (d) TX-100 + H₂O + NaCl (0.075 M). (O) 288.15, (Δ) 293.15, ($\square$) 298.15 K.

ent study we report the data for critical micelle concentration (CMC), surface pressure at CMC (π_{cmc}), surface excess concentration (Γ_{max}), minimum area per molecule at the air-liquid interface (A_{min}), and thermodynamic parameters of micellization/adsorption for iso-octyl phenoxy polyethoxy-ethanol (TX-100) in water and in aqueous sodium chloride at 288.15, 293.15 and 298.15 K.

Results and discussion

Plots of surface tension versus log [surfactant] for the studied systems are given in Fig. 1. The critical micelle concentration (CMC) values obtained from the sharp break point in above plots are given in Table 1. It is clear that CMC values decrease with increase in temperature (Table 1). The process of micelle formation is controlled by hydrophobic interaction as well as London dispersion force⁴. In the case of nonionic surfactants, in the absence of any additive, the depression in CMC may due to the dehydration of the hydrophobic moiety of the surfactant molecules and also due to breaking of water structure with increasing temperature⁵. It follows from Table 1 that the CMC value of the surfactant decreases with the addition of sodium chloride. The effect of NaCl on the CMC value of TX-100 may be partly due to the salting out of the hydrated ethylene oxide condensate of the surfactant and partly due to ion-dipole interaction (in the Stern layer) of Na⁺ and negative dipole of the hydroxyl group of the surfactant⁶.

Maximum surface excess concentration (Γ_{max}) values at the air-liquid interface has been obtained using Gibb's adsorption equation²

$$\Gamma_{max} = -1/2.303 nRT (d\gamma/d \log C)_T \quad (1)$$

where *n* is the number of particles released per surfactant molecule in the solution and *R*, the gas constant. $(d\gamma/d \log C)_T$ represents the slope of the surface tension versus log *C* plot below the CMC at constant temperature *T*. In the present investigation *n* = 1 for nonionic surfactant. The calculated values for Γ_{max} for the studied systems at three temperatures are also presented in Table 1. It may be seen that the Γ_{max} values decrease with the increase in temperature which may be due to the enhanced molecular thermal agitation at higher temperature which is in conformity with earlier results⁷. A further decrease in Γ_{max} values in the presence of aqueous NaCl may be due to the fact that addition of electrolyte causes a partial displacement of surfactant molecules from the air-liquid interface to the bulk phase.

The minimum area per molecule (A_{min}) at the liquid-air interface was calculated using the following equation

$$A_{min} = 10^{14}/N \Gamma_{max} \quad (2)$$

where *N* is Avogadro's number. A_{min} values for the studied

systems are given in the Table 1. An examination of these values revealed that A_{min} increases both with the increase in temperature as well as with the concentration of NaCl in the surfactant solution. This behaviour can be explained in terms of the enhanced compatibility of surfactant with the solvent in the presence of electrolyte, thereby, causing a shift of surfactant molecules from air-liquid interface to the bulk phase.

Surface pressure at CMC (π_{cmc}), an index of surface tension reduction at CMC, was calculated using the equation²,

$$\pi_{cmc} = \gamma_0 - \gamma_{cmc} \quad (3)$$

where γ_0 = surface tension of water and γ_{cmc} = surface tension of surfactant solution at CMC. π_{cmc} values are presented in Table 1. π_{cmc} only marginally increase with increase in temperature.

Table 1. Critical micelle concentration (cmc), surface excess concentration (Γ_{max}), minimum area per molecule (A_{min}) and surface pressure at cmc (π_{cmc}) for iso-octylphenoxy polyethoxyethanol (TX-100) in water and in aqueous electrolyte systems

[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temperature (K)	CMC × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	$\Gamma_{max} \times 10^{10}$ (mol cm ⁻²)	$A_{min} \times 10^2$ (nm ²)	$\pi_{cmc} \times 10^3$ (Nm ⁻¹)
0	288.15	0.97	1.86	89.26	37.69
	293.15	0.89	1.84	90.23	38.85
	298.15	0.81	1.71	97.09	39.17
0.025	288.15	0.93	1.72	96.53	37.69
	293.15	0.85	1.68	98.83	37.95
	298.15	0.78	1.61	103.12	39.37
0.050	288.15	0.89	1.70	97.66	38.80
	293.15	0.80	1.63	101.86	39.00
	298.15	0.71	1.59	104.42	40.47
0.075	288.15	0.82	1.63	101.86	39.09
	293.15	0.72	1.58	105.08	39.25
	298.15	0.68	1.48	112.18	39.77

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of the micellization/adsorption for iso-octyl phenoxy polyethoxy ethanol (TX-100) in water and in aqueous electrolyte systems

[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temperature (K)	$-\Delta C_m^0/(-\Delta C_s^0)$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H_m^0/(\Delta H_s^0)$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta S_m^0/(\Delta S_s^0)$ (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
0	288.15	26.25/(28.28)	11.79/(14.37)	0.132/(0.148)
	293.15	26.91/(29.02)	12.96/(18.47)	0.136/(0.162)
	298.15	27.61/(29.90)	14.13/(22.57)	0.140/(0.176)
0.025	288.15	26.35/(28.54)	11.11/(14.68)	0.130/(0.150)
	293.15	27.03/(29.29)	12.58/(17.91)	0.135/(0.161)
	298.15	27.70/(30.15)	14.04/(21.13)	0.140/(0.172)
0.050	288.15	26.45/(28.73)	14.16/(19.10)	0.142/(0.166)
	293.15	27.17/(29.56)	15.04/(22.33)	0.144/(0.177)
	298.15	27.93/(30.50)	15.63/(25.55)	0.146/(0.188)
0.075	288.15	26.65/(28.95)	14.27/(22.34)	0.142/(0.178)
	293.15	27.36/(29.84)	15.44/(25.27)	0.146/(0.188)
	298.15	28.04/(30.83)	16.61/(28.20)	0.150/(0.198)

The thermodynamic parameters like standard Gibb's energy change of micellisation ΔC_m^0 , ΔH_m^0 and ΔS_m^0 have been calculated using the eqs. (4), (5) and (6), respectively².

thermodynamic parameters like standard Gibbs's energy change of micellisation ΔG_m^0 , ΔH_m^0 and ΔS_m^0 have been calculated using the eqs. (4), (5) and (6), respectively².

$$\Delta G_m^0 = RT \ln X \quad (4)$$

(where X is the surfactant mole fraction at CMC)

$$\Delta S_m^0 = [-d(\Delta G_m^0)/dT]_p \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta H_m^0 = \Delta G_m^0 + T\Delta S_m^0 \quad (6)$$

The various thermodynamic parameters of micellization calculated using eqs. (4–6) are presented in Table 2. The ΔG_m^0 values are found to be negative indicating the spontaneity of micellization process in aqueous system. The ΔS_m^0 values are positive for the studied systems. It may be due to structure breaking of water when the surfactant hydrophobic chain transfers from bulk water to the micellar core. There is a further increase in ΔS_m^0 on adding NaCl to the surfactant solution which may be partly due to water structure breaking effect of NaCl and partly due to the desolvation of prehydrated ethylene oxide chains of surfactant molecules in the presence of NaCl.

The standard enthalpy of micellization ΔH_m^0 is positive due to the hydrophobic-hydrophobic interaction of surfactant alkyl chain in the process of micellization of nonionic surfactant (TX-100).

Thermodynamic parameters of adsorption viz. ΔG_a^0 , ΔH_a^0 and ΔS_a^0 were calculated using the following relations at constant pressure⁸.

$$\Delta G_a^0 = \Delta G_m^0 - 6.023 \times 10^{-1} \pi_{cmc} A_{min} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S_a^0 = -d(\Delta G_a^0)/dT \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta H_a^0 = \Delta G_a^0 + T\Delta S_a^0 \quad (9)$$

The values of ΔG_a^0 , ΔH_a^0 and ΔS_a^0 are presented in Table 2. The lower ΔG_a^0 values compared to ΔG_m^0 (Table 2) indicate that adsorption of the surfactant molecules at the air-liquid interface is preferred over the micellization. The ΔS_a^0 values are all positive and larger than ΔS_m^0 . This may be due to more degree of freedom of the surfactant molecules at the air-liquid interface compared to that in the cramped interior of micelle⁹.

The endothermic ΔH_a^0 may be due to the breaking of H-bonds between polyoxyethylene chain oxygen of surfactant and water molecules at the air-liquid interface.

Experimental

The nonionic surfactant iso-octylphenoxypolyethoxy ethanol (TX-100) (S. D. fine, purity 98%) and sodium chloride (NaCl) (B.D.H., purity 99.9%) used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in the doubly distilled water having a specific conductance of $2.00 \times 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K.

Surface tensions of solutions were determined from dropweight method using a specially designed stalagmometer as described by Jain *et al.*¹⁰. The stalagmometer was calibrated by determining the surface tension of pure liquids : benzene, carbon tetrachloride, n-hexane, acetophenone and water as standard. Reproducibility of results were within $\pm 0.2\%$ literature values. The measurements were made in a thermostat (Tempstar, Model KW 201 A), which provided temperature control within ± 0.01 K.

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